

Towards Equitable Open Access: Reimagining Publishing Practices for Applied Linguistics

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Abstract

In recent years, the field of applied linguistics has made significant strides towards more transparent research practices. Journals in our field almost always offer options for open access publication and wonderful repositories have been developed that allow scholars to share their research instruments, analysis scripts, and datasets. This leads to more transparency and better opportunities to profit from each other's wisdom. We have also witnessed the creation of databases that make our research accessible far beyond academic communities, such as the OASIS database and the Language Learning Task Bank, which significantly contribute to increasing the impact of the research generated by our field.

These valuable developments are driven by our desire to be more visible as scholars, to produce better research, and to allow anyone to benefit from our findings. Meanwhile, the publishing industry has recognized these desires and has managed to turn open access publication into a highly profitable enterprise. Publishing open access has become big business to such a large extent that our goals of increased transparency, equity, and better science are jeopardized. Open access publishing is primarily available to affluent scholars, and so-called 'predatory' publishing has emerged, which is driven more by economic concerns than quality concerns. These developments pose serious threats to the diversity and trustworthiness of the research our field generates. In this contribution, I will delve into these dynamics, discuss the forces at play, and offer suggestions for how we can move towards publication practices that are truly equitable.

Towards Equitable Open Access: Reimagining Publishing Practices for Applied Linguistics

If you work in academia, you will have gotten used to the many messages we receive from publishers, conference organizers, journals, etc. We receive invitations to speak in the most exotic places across the world, to become editor or guest editor for journals, or to submit our work to a particular journal. We also receive triumphant messages explaining how journal impact factors have increased. There is no end to the messages we get, luring us towards submission of our work to these outlets. Luckily, most of these messages end up in our spam filters and if I inspect my spam folders, then there is honestly no field of science that I haven't received invitations for. These messages are symptoms of a broken Open Access publication system. In this contribution, I will dive into the machinery behind this, and explain why I am concerned about the future of open access publishing. I have two main concerns. First, the current system leads to inequity, probably even more so than we had prior to the advent of OA. Second, it undermines research quality and the overall trustworthiness of science. My overall aim is to raise awareness that the open access movement itself may be in danger, and why we as the field of applied linguistics should reconsider our publication practices. I will end this contribution with recommendations for authors, editors and academic societies.

A brief history of open access publishing

I can look back on about 30 years of academic publishing. When I started as a student at the University of Groningen in the early nineties, the publishing field was very different. I could only read physical copies of papers, often bound in readers for the purpose of a particular course. Or I would go to the library and find the latest issue of *Studies in Second Language Acquisition* or *Language Learning* on public display. Earlier issues could be found in bound volumes on one of the many shelves in the library. Scientific publication was entirely subscription based. Things changed quickly, however, due to

the advent of the world wide web and the development of the portable document format, which allowed online documents to have a definitive form.

As academic publishing took on a more digital form, calls for open access publication arose, as well as discussions on how to organize open access publication financially. An important development towards open access publishing was the establishment of the Creative Commons licensing system in 2002, that allows authors to mark their work as their intellectual property with a free legal license. Another important event was the Budapest Open Access Initiative (*Budapest Open Access Initiative – Make Research Publicly Available*, n.d.). At a meeting organized in 2001, financial models for open access publication were discussed and in an ensuing declaration, they advocated for so-called gold open access models of publication. Academic publication should no longer be subscription-based, but open access should be arranged by means of a one-off Author Processing Charge (APC). Soon after, for-profit gold open access publishers entered the market (e.g., Frontiers, PLOS, etc.). This changed the publication market quite substantially and required existing publishers to respond. In the 2010s, they did by flipping their journals to gold models or by exploiting a hybrid model based on a combination of subscription and gold open access. This latter model has become the dominant option within the humanities and the social sciences (L.-A. Butler et al., 2023). In other fields of science, gold is the dominant model.

In 2015, the first so-called transformative agreement (also called ‘read-and-publish’ agreements) was signed between Springer/Nature and the universities of the Netherlands. This allowed scholars working at Dutch universities (scholars at Dutch Universities of Applied Science were – and still are – not part of the deal) to publish OA in all Springer/Nature journals. Within a few years there were contracts with all big publishers and the model has spread and now allows many scholars in our field to publish open access. Meanwhile, many scholars have advocated so-called green open access publishing. This means that scholars make preprints available in open repositories. Green open access often occurs in addition to conventional publication. Green makes research accessible fast, because you don’t have to wait for the lengthy review procedures. For many scholars that don’t have the possibility to pay author

processing charges, the green route is the only way of making their work openly available.

We have also seen signs of concern and discontent with existing publishing models. In 2015, for example, a remarkable step was taken by the editorial board of *Lingua*. They abandoned their journal at Elsevier for ideological reasons and established *Glossa*. It was an early sign of discontent with publishers' reluctance to embrace open access. Another noteworthy event was the organization of another Budapest Open Access Initiative conference. Here, all forms of commercial open access sciences were now denounced.

Open access developments in applied linguistics

It is probably fair to say that the humanities have generally been slow to adopt OA, but applied linguists have been among the front runners within the field of humanities. In 2004, McVeigh (2004) counted 239 open access journals in total, yet only four fell within the arts and humanities domain. One of these four was the journal *Language Learning and Technology* – launched in 1997 and most likely the first OA journal in our field. We have seen many wonderful developments towards open science in applied linguistics, of which I'd like to highlight a few that have been important in my work.

A magnificent development was the launch of the IRIS database in 2011, a field-specific repository of research instruments that many of us contribute to and download from. I would also like to highlight the establishment of the *Journal of the European Second Language Association (JESLA)* in 2017. JESLA is an example of a community-based open access journal that charges no fees to authors for publishing in it. It adheres to the so-called diamond open access model, where open access is financed by members of the EuroSLA society. Since then, EuroSLA has run an open access journal as well as an open access book series under the name of *EuroSLA Studies*. Another development that I'm really proud to have been part of was the establishment of OASIS (Open Accessible Summaries In Language Studies) (Marsden et al., 2018). OASIS has proven very effective in making research accessible both physically as well as conceptually for audiences working outside of academia. A final mention is for *Applied*

Linguistics Press (ALP), an open access book publisher launched in 2023, offering a very interesting open access alternative for anyone seeking to publish a book (*Applied Linguistics Press*, 2026).

Apart from these more tangible outputs, we have also seen lots of leadership by many colleagues in the field and it would be impossible to do them justice within the scope of this article. As a result of their work, at this point in the movement towards open science, most of us hopefully feel a strong moral imperative to work as openly as possible. Open science practices make scientific knowledge available to everyone in and outside of academia; they increase the scientific and societal impact of the work we do; they allow us to properly understand how scientific knowledge is generated and to re-use and build on each other's work, and they promote the quality and rigour of the work that we do (e.g., Liu & Marsden, 2024; Marsden & Morgan-Short, 2023; Marsden & Plonsky, 2018; McManus, 2024; Plonsky, 2024b; Porte & McManus, 2018). Colleagues in the field have accordingly encouraged open access publication, and urged us to share our research instruments, analysis tools and even our data (e.g., Bolibaugh et al., 2021; Isbell, 2024; Mackey et al., 2024; Marsden et al., 2015; Mizumoto, 2024). We have also gone further. We also developed excellent platforms for making this possible, such as the IRIS-database, the Task bank, the OASIS database, and open access publishing venues (e.g., Gurzynski-Weiss & IATBLT, n.d.; Marsden et al., 2015, 2018; Plonsky, 2024a).

The current system of open access publication

Overall, we have seen many good developments. Despite our best efforts, however, I am not necessarily confident that we'll continue to develop in the right direction. I am particularly concerned about the development of open access publication. The current system of open access publication seems to naturally gravitate toward inequity and pseudoscience. In this section, I will describe this. I will discuss practices and cases that many of us may somehow be involved in, and I want to emphasize that my problem is with the system, not with the players. Everyone of us has very good reasons to do the things we do, and we find ourselves in a system that is rapidly changing beyond our

control. None of us are to blame for that, nor is anyone to blame for using the system to develop our careers.

The cost of open access

In the past decade, we have seen a steady increase in the share of OA publications. The OA dashboard maintained by the STM association shows that open access has been on the rise ('OA Dashboard', n.d.). However, it also shows that open access shares seem to have plateaued at approximately 50% of the total number of papers published, which is somewhat worrying. A check of fourteen of the most prominent applied linguistics journals offers an almost identical picture. In 2025, 45% of the papers appeared open access, and there was hardly any growth in open access shares from 2024 to 2025. It seems that the growth in OA publication is levelling off, also within applied linguistics.

It is reasonable to assume that the cost of open access is putting a brake on the growth. In 2022, Butler et al. (2023) estimated that the average Author Processing Charge (APC) for hybrid journals was 2900 dollars. A inspection of the prices within our field suggests that prices have risen dramatically within 4 years time. In the first months of 2026, the average APC for fourteen prominent AL journals amounted to 3790 dollars excluding taxes. The journal *Applied Linguistics*, published by Oxford University Press, charges authors a staggering 5755 dollars for making their work open access. You may wonder: what is the true cost of publishing an academic paper? There is no easy answer to this question and I wasn't able to find out how big publishers calculate their fees. If we take the publishers' profit margins as an indication, then they should be substantially lower. A few years ago, the Fair Open Access Alliance estimated that an OA publication should not cost more than 1000 dollars or 50 dollars per page (*Fair Open Access Alliance*, n.d.). At the *Dutch Journal of Applied Linguistics*, we do it for much less.

The steep prices clearly are a source of inequity. They are barriers to open access. Many scholars cannot afford the fees, which means that they have to publish behind a paywall and accept that their papers are less accessible. Ayeni et al. (2025) conducted an interview study to investigate to what extent OA publishing is equitable, i.e., equally accessible for everyone. Their data show that there are cost-barriers, but

also barriers associated with career stage, privilege, gender, and institutional policies. We also know that the open access fees are a barrier for scholars in the global south (Kwon, 2022). There is of course the option of going green, i.e., archiving a preprint in an open repository. However, most scholars need their work to be peer reviewed for it to be recognized. While it does improve accessibility of research, it may also contribute to the perpetuation of the current, problematic system if authors feel that green publishing is all they can do to make science more open and do not also strive towards better alternatives (Andringa et al., 2024).

Transformative agreements

In the Netherlands, I have been able to publish under so-called ‘transformative agreements’ for a decade now. Transformative agreements allow scholars to publish OA because their university or research institute has already paid for open access. Initially, I was very pleased about these deals and I have profited a lot from them. Most of my research is openly available because of transformative agreements. Recently, however, I got to experience how expensive OA is. It turned out that a paper that was accepted in November was not eligible for open access publication, because the nationally agreed fund for open access had reached its limit, meaning that no one in the Netherlands was able to publish open access with this publisher if their paper was accepted in November and December. Research funded by the Dutch Research Council has to appear open access, and so we were obligated to pay €4,200 for open access. This will have to go at the expense of either research assistance or the societal impact activities that we had planned. It is unclear how much it costs to publish papers under these deals, and they probably vary in different contexts. It is clear, though, that it is not necessarily cheaper to publish under these deals. In fact, some of these agreements are known to be exorbitant: Van Noorden (2020) describes an agreement between the German Max Planck Institute and Springer/Nature that amounted to 11.200 dollars per article.

Transformative agreements strongly work in favor of the big publishers with large portfolios. It strengthens their hold on the publishing market. Small publishers suffer, because they cannot easily strike deals with so many parties, which means that their

journals become less attractive to publish in. Transformative agreements also deepen the existing inequities: Rich institutions and affluent countries can afford these deals (Andringa et al., 2024; Marsden & Morgan-Short, 2023). Many publishers have some kind of philanthropic program, but scholars in Brazil, for example, cannot profit from such philanthropy, and are facing insurmountable cost for open access publishing (Kowaltowski et al., 2022). Within more affluent contexts, unwanted differences arise as well. In the Netherlands, scholars at Universities of Applied Sciences do not have transformative publishing agreements, and they find it much harder to publish open access.

Excessive profits

I already suggested that OA fees are far too high, and if you look at big publishers, then this impression is confirmed. OA is big business. The profit margins in academic publishing are staggering. RELX, the company behind Elsevier, reported a profit margin of 35%, while Springer/Nature reported a profit margin of 29% for the first half of 2025 (Follow the Money; Ties Gijzel). The CEO's of the big publishers are consistently in the list of best paid CEO's. Only big tech companies can rival these profit margins, but please note that these publishing profits are made by charging authors to publish their publicly funded research. In recent years, publishers' growth was primarily based on APC revenues. Haustein et al. investigated APC revenues paid to six big publishers and found they have tripled between 2019 and 2023 (Haustein et al., 2024). It is no surprise, then, that Frank Vrancken Peeters, CEO of Springer Nature said: "Research contributes most when it's openly accessible". By incorporating gold open access into their publication models, big publishers have averted the danger of scientists turning away from their journals. Please note that hybrid journals, that are the dominant type in the Humanities and collect open access fees as well as subscription fees, are the most expensive to publish in.

Clearly, publishers have huge commercial interests to protect and so appear to have doubled down on their marketing activities. That's why we get many messages from publishers that somehow try to alert us to their portfolios. In Andringa et al. (2024), we

discuss another marketing trick that publishers use to strengthen their hold on the publication market. We describe how the new journal *Research Methods in Applied Linguistics* was launched, which is a wonderful journal run by brilliant scholars. However, the way it was established conveys how open access has become a money machine for publishers. In the first two years, authors were given free open access. All papers appeared open access, and the journal attracted an impressive set of contributions. Within a few years, it established a good impact factor according to Elsevier's own metrics, and now the paywalls are up. Here, open access was misused to quickly establish a new journal and strengthen Elsevier's position in the market.

In a recent letter, The Young Academy of Groningen warned against a situation in which the entire academic system is becoming dependent on a few highly commercial players in the publication market and how we become dependent on their services (The Young Academy Groningen & The Open Science Community Groningen, personal communication, 10 July 2023). They show how Elsevier is trying to monetize every step in the research process by offering tools and services that make our research life easier. Think of applications like Science Direct, Mendeley, Scopus, Pure, etc. Other big publishers are employing similar activities. The Young Academy alerts us to risks associated with this. One concerns privacy and data protection: commercial companies know a frightening lot about your research activities and on the basis of this, would be able to compile very extensive reports of your research performance. For this reason, some scholars in the Netherlands have refused to enter their publications into Pure, Elsevier's research evaluation system. Another risk is financial: there is a risk of so-called vendor-lock in. This means that the research production cycle is becoming so heavily dependent on these services that you cannot retract from them. If you cannot retract, then Elsevier can easily increase their prices, making research far more costly than it should be. Here we also see a clear source of inequity emerge, because these services can be bought more readily in certain contexts, offering researchers in these contexts substantial advantages.

Citation metrics

Often, messages we receive from publishers are triumphant notifications explaining how impact factors for a particular journal have gone up. Having good journal impact factors is important to publishers, because they are important to researchers.

Researchers are often required to publish in high impact journals, or want to for their careers. In a highly commercialized and competitive publication market, citation metrics become even more problematic (Fong et al., 2023; Onstad, 2024; Onstad & Sime, 2024). Research has shown that publishers exert pressure on editorial boards to work towards higher journal impact factors. This leads to practices that are not necessarily conducive to better quality science. To increase journal impact factors, journals will want to publish more reviews studies or methodological papers, because these tend to be interesting to wide audiences and generally attract more citations. This pressure also leads to so-called coercion: Editors requesting that papers in their journals are cited (Fong et al., 2023). This is especially questionable if done at or after acceptance.

Another effect is that editors are encouraged to consider: Will this paper be cited? We experienced this ourselves with a paper on LESLLA learners (emerging readers learning a second language). It got desk rejections, saying explicitly: “This is a good paper, but we don’t think it will have much impact”. I wonder if we would have received this comment had we used university student participants and pretended that what we found was universally true. Together with Aline Godfroid, I’ve pointed to the dangers of biased sampling and what that may mean for the impact of our science (Andringa & Godfroid, 2020; Godfroid & Andringa, 2023). Clearly the current publication system provides a perverse incentive towards highly generalizable studies, studies with large audiences, or with participants of whom there are many. This disincentivises research with marginalized groups, which leads to their further marginalization.

Research evaluation

Citation metrics may also be used in research evaluation procedures as indicators of how impactful a researcher or a particular study is. They often play a role in decisions about whether we are appointed, receive a promotion, whether our lab is doing well

enough, and whether we receive funding. Hence, they may weigh quite heavily on how our careers develop. In many ways, this is unfortunate, because citation metrics were not developed to be research quality indicators and really only measure how often a study is cited. If our careers are determined by quantity measures, then this is what is promoted: quantity. Quantity can be an indicator of how well we are doing as researchers, and of how productive we are, but it offers a very limited view. Research quality also involves things like methodological rigour, originality, and societal value (Aksnes et al., 2019). These things all take time and they are naturally devalued in a research assessment system that prioritizes impact through citations and publication quantity. It leads to undue pressures to publish, and if you browse scholarly databases, you can find many accounts in the literature of the associated negative consequences: publication pressure is associated with bullying, low mental wellbeing, publication in predatory venues, and a deemphasis on methodological rigour (Mutongoza, 2023).

This is acknowledged in Frameworks such as DORA and CoARA, which strive towards fairer ways of research assessment, in which citation metrics play no more than a secondary role. In the Netherlands, this has led to a national programme called ‘Erkennen & Waarderen’ (Recognition & Rewards). This programme recognizes that we need diversity in skills in academia and works towards a more balanced assessment scheme, in which impact, teaching and leadership are valued and assessed alongside research. In doing so, the program aims to promote collaboration and team science. ‘Publish or perish’ is also very present in Dutch academia, but the effects of the program are visible, for example when we apply for a grant: our cv needs to be written as a narrative and has a word limit, we are not allowed to include impact metrics, and we can show only ten references of your own work, which are preferably not just references to academic papers.

Predatory publishing and paper mills

As editor of DuJAL, I also regularly get messages from companies wanting to acquire our journal. They probably are a logical aberration of the current open access publication climate. Money can be made off our research and our research outlets, and many

predatory publishers and journals have emerged in recent years. These are fake or fraudulent publishers whose only interest is that we pay them an open access fee. As a result, they often have very poor and very fast peer review policies. They may overrule reviewers if they are too negative, or may list fake editorial boards. They often use logo's and names that resemble those of respectable journals, etc. It can be difficult to identify predatory journals and boundaries are fuzzy. In an interesting study, Nejadghanbar et al. (2023) surveyed authors who published in predatory journals. They found that lack of awareness was but one reason to publish in these journals. Other reasons were high pressure to publish, being unsuccessful to publish in top-tier journals, and failure to recognize the journal as predatory. A group of scholars who wish to remain anonymous keep a list, and it contains almost 2780 journals (*Predatory Journals*, n.d.). These journals publish open access work that then enters the public domain, while the work itself may well be questionable and should sometimes not be published.

Similarly, academic fraud has developed new dimensions with the advent of APC-based open access paper publication. Parker et al. (2024) describe the paper mill industry, which can provide fabricated datasets and papers and favourable peer-reviews for you. One way of doing this is by infiltrating existing journals. Ansalde describes a case in El País of the journal for the Science of the Total Environment – an Elsevier journal. Ansalde describes how the journal increased its publications from 1000 articles per year to 10.000 articles per year against an APC of more than 4000 dollars per article, which must have meant 41 million dollars in annual revenues for this journal alone. However, it was put on hold because the scientific quality had become questionable. This case illustrates that questionable and predatory practices also occur at publishers that we tend to trust. Broersma (2024), for example, points to discussions about Frontiers, a gold open access publisher. Guest editors have reported to have been pressured to accept papers that received unfavorable reviews. This too, leads to the validation of poor science.

Generative AI

What happens if large language models are let loose in this moribund system? I find it incredibly complex to imagine how AI will shape academic publishing. If we look at the absolute number of papers published in academia, then we can see a very clear rise in published papers between 2023 and 2024 ('OA Dashboard', n.d.). Is this a good sign or bad sign? In an online commentary, Baldwin and Borchert (2026) point to promises and perils of AI. A promise can be that AI can be a democratizing force, if it allows good scholars to overcome language barriers in academic publishing. At the same time, well written articles are not necessarily methodologically sound. My job as editor at DuJAL has become more difficult. It has become harder to spot poor quality research in the submissions we receive at DuJAL and there is a worry on the board that we inadvertently admit research that should not be admitted to the public domain. Wingfield and Wingfield (2025) voice concerns about the consequences of inequity in open access publication: It means that some people's voices are more present in the public domain, and AI systems, which rely heavily on openly available texts, tend to be sensitive to this. Big publishers are now rolling out AI-based journal management systems. Hopefully, they are immune to the differences in visibility of scholars that can and cannot afford open access.

Reimagining open access publication in applied linguistics

The current system of open access publication gravitates towards inequity and puts unprecedented pressure on the quality of the knowledge that the field is generating. Inequity is present along many divides: there is Global South–Global North divide, but there are also early- vs. late-career divides, gender divides, and quite a few other divides associated with some kind of privilege. Many of us are deeply involved in this system as authors. We are editors at journals that have been around for decades and that has fundamentally shaped scientific discussion in our field, and we are rightfully proud to be that editor. However, we also have to face reality and acknowledge that we somehow – while we didn't want to – have become part of a publication system that is highly problematic. The great irony is that our push towards open access publication has developed into an unsustainable situation that now presents a danger to the open

access movement itself. Hence, we urgently need to reconsider what it is that we are striving for. Open access, yes, because we do not want to return to publication behind paywalls. But what kind of open access?

The answer to this question is not difficult. Diamond is the answer (Andringa et al., 2024). Diamond open access refers to publishing articles open access at no cost to authors or their institutions. This sounds simple, but it is actually quite difficult to define diamond open access. For example, we can already see publishers appropriating the concept by sometimes offering diamond open access in ways that still exploit the existing, highly commercialized structures. Earlier, I discussed the Budapest Open Access Initiative in 2002, where gold open access was embraced as a way towards making research openly available. In 2022, there was another meeting, and now all forms of commercial scientific publishing are denounced. Their recommendations are that we host OA research on open and non-commercial infrastructures, that we reform research assessment practices to reward diamond publishing; that we prioritize platforms that do not exclude authors on economic grounds, hence abandon APC-based publishing; and that we consider the goals of open science when we spend open science funds (*Budapest Open Access Initiative – Make Research Publicly Available*, n.d.).

Diamond publication platforms as well as impact platforms often struggle financially. Academic publishing does not need to be expensive, but it is not free either. Journals that receive support from academic societies generally do well, but financial viability can be difficult to achieve for diamond journals, book publishers and sharing platforms (i.e., OASIS, IRIS, ALP, the task bank, etc.). OASIS, for example, is hugely successful in communicating our science to audiences outside of academia, but it is fragile financially. The survival of these kinds of initiatives often rests on the donation of time and effort by devoted researchers, their research institutes, and their success in acquiring funds. What if we took our next paper to a diamond journal and donated the unspent open access fee to open access initiatives? A donation of \$4000 dollars, for example, could already make a tremendous difference for OASIS. It would allow us to

appoint an assistant for eight months, who could help keep metadata in shape, liaise with editors, users and the technical team, keep the website up to date, etc.

In reimagining open access publication, there are three key components of academic publishing that I would like to highlight: peer review, ownership and transparency. The justification for the existence of academic journals in this day and age lies almost exclusively in peer review, in the possibility that journals offer of having your work assessed and validated by peers in the field. Having research validated by (human) peers may well be the most important quality stamp any study can receive. At the same time, peer review is becoming increasingly difficult to organize due to the rise in journal submissions and reviewer fatigue (Adam, 2025; Silver et al., 2023). For this reason, ownership of this process is important. Peer review should always be in the hands of trusted parties and will also be more easy to organize. It should be in the hands of scholars and academic societies who know the scientific field inside out, who can organize this process responsibly and ethically, and who can be trusted to adhere to the principles of diamond open access.

The third key component is transparency. Radical transparency is probably the only way forward in the system that we find ourselves in. This means availability of instruments, protocols and datasets during review and at publication, a drum that many colleagues have already beaten (e.g., Bolibaugh et al., 2021; Isbell, 2024; Marsden & Morgan-Short, 2023). It seems only logical to publish these in one place, which would mean that publishing platforms are more than just vehicles for academic articles. However, other systems are also conceivable. The new journal MetaROR (metaror.org), for example, a journal on meta-research, requires authors to submit articles to preprint servers, making the work open access immediately. The journal then organizes review and publishes the entire review process upon acceptance.

Towards diamond open access

It has been argued that change requires both publishing reform and Research assessment reform (Waltman, 2025). This lies largely outside of our powers. Yet, we may have more power than we think. Aczel et al. (2021) estimated that reviewers donated

more than 100 million hours of their time to peer review in the year 2020. This is labour offered to publishers that goes unpaid. They also estimated that American scholars contributed 16% of these review hours, and calculated that this amounted to 1.5 billion dollars. This excludes all the time that we invest in editorship. These are empowering numbers. This is time that we own and that we give, and we can always decide to devote some of this time to something else. If we did that with just a small fraction of the time we invest in review, it could make a huge difference for open science.

A few years ago, our research group launched a survey into open access publication practices. We asked scholars in the language sciences to imagine that they wrote a good quality paper that would stand a chance in one of the better journals. We gave them two journal options and asked them to choose. Journal A was fairly new, with a small publisher and had low impact and prestige. Journal B was a longstanding journal with a large publisher and a high impact factor. Given this choice, only 10% opted for submission to Journal A, all else being equal. However, if journal A offered free open access, then 46% would bring their paper to this journal, even when they had the funds to publish OA in journal B. This shift shows that many scholars are sensitive to the cost of publishing. When that journal was carried by an editorial board of high-profile scholars, then 84% would bring their paper to Journal A, despite its low impact factor. This too demonstrates how much power we have. If a journal has status, it is because we confer that status on the journal. It is our reputations, our editing time, and our reviewing time that make a journal valuable. Accordingly, it is for us to decide which journals are prestigious.

At this point, when I want to offer suggestions for actions we can take towards change, I want to acknowledge that I am aware of my privilege. As a scholar working in the Netherlands, I am privileged in more ways than I realize, but certainly also in terms of open access publishing. In Europe, and in the Netherlands, the push towards open science has been quite strong. In 2015, the first transformative agreement was signed between Springer/Nature and the Dutch Academy of Sciences. This means that I have been able to publish open access in many good journals for over a decade now and virtually all of my work is open access. For publicly funded research, this is also an

obligation. The Netherlands has had an open science grant scheme (that also contributed towards OASIS). For diamond open access more specifically, several instruments and services exist. There is a diamond OA expertise center to help scholars, editors, etc. towards diamond publishing. There is a nationally maintained journal management system for diamond journals: Openjournals.nl. This is also the platform that DuJAL runs on. Several university presses also offer this service. In December 2025, the Dutch Research Council granted 1.5 million euros towards the further development of diamond open infrastructures. Finally, the research council also opened a grant scheme for flipping journals. Editorial boards can apply for money if they wish to move away from a commercial publisher.

As we have also argued in *Diamond is a scientist's best friend*, change needs to be driven by those with privilege (Andringa et al., 2024). Late career scholars, for example, will experience fewer negative consequences if they opt for publication in lower tier, but diamond journals. In addition, their submissions and editorial support will be crucial towards elevating the status of these journals and would likely encourage many others to follow suit. The survey we conducted supports this, as it showed that 84 percent of the scholars in our field would be inclined to submit their work to lower impact journals if high profile scholars are associated with it. It is important to keep in mind, though, that things like journal selection in author teams need to be discussed with care and consideration for the interests of all involved. The last thing we need is supervisors forcing their PhD students to take their papers to diamond venues when that is not in their interest.

The applied linguistics community

As a community of science, what we need first and foremost is a good range of attractive diamond open access publication platforms. Such journals already exist: *Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching*, *Language Learning and Technology*, and the *Journal of the European Second Language Association (JESLA)* are just three wonderful examples (for a list of journals, see Al-Hoorie's webpage: *Applied Linguistics Open Access Journals*, n.d.), as are *Applied Linguistics Press* and *EuroSLA Studies* for book

publishing. But many more are needed. The hardest part of open access publishing has always been working out viable financial structures (D. Butler, 2003; Dufour et al., 2023; Yoon et al., 2024), and I do not want to make this sound simple. Diamond open access has always been easiest to realize on the basis of some kind of community support. However, within each of our contexts, possibilities for support likely exist and international initiatives are being developed as well. For example, DuJAL recently joined the OJC, which seeks to establish financial support for diamond journals by collectively looking for sponsorships from libraries, funders, etc. (*Open Journals Collective*, n.d.)

Authors

As scientists and authors of research reports, critical awareness of the machinery in academic publishing and our position in this system is of paramount importance. This will allow us to recognize and question particular publication practices and platforms and help us weigh the best and most responsible publication option for our work. Publishing open access continues to be of the utmost importance, as it allows many researchers across the world to read academic publications who do not readily have access to research published behind paywalls. However, while gold open access allows everyone access to your work, it is important to be aware that many colleagues simply cannot afford it, creating inequity in publishing opportunities. Hence, we should publish our work in diamond venues if possible, or choose gold if this is the best option and if budget is available. If neither works and our work ends up behind a paywall, then we can publish preprints or postprints in open repositories (consider signing the postprint pledge: Al-Hoorie & Hiver, 2023). Broersma (2024) recommends civil disobedience: She has posted publisher versions of her research articles on her personal website for many years now. In addition, there are several other things that we could do:

- Having our work validated by peers is the core purpose of academic journals. This means that we should definitely continue to make ourselves available for peer review, but we should also consider carefully for what journals we do reviews. Reviewing for predatory journals is a waste of time, as our opinions

simply do not matter much to them. Perhaps it is possible to divert some reviewing time to support diamond open access platforms.

- Similarly, if asked for editorial jobs, carefully consider the journal and its policies. We can ask critical questions and let editorial boards and publishers know that this topic matters to us.
- It should also be evident that we should refrain from launching new journals with commercial publishers.
- If you are applying for a grant, consider including reservations for open access causes if you plan to make use of them.
- A final recommendation I would like to make is that we support academic and professional societies as much as we can, especially if they run a diamond journal. Your membership is sorely needed.

Editors

Perhaps the most important point to keep in mind for editors is to develop a mature vision on the impact your journal is aiming for. Journals will typically want to advance scientific enquiry into certain topics and themes, contribute to methodological development and be of societal relevance or relevance to practice. These missions should be at the heart of decisions about acceptance in your journals. As soon as citation metrics become part of these decisions, you are devaluing these core values. In addition, it sends a message to the field about what kind of research is valued. Your decisions have substantial consequences for authors, as they shape research evaluation procedures in their host institutions. Hence, it is important to resist the urge to prioritize papers based on the likelihood that they attract many citations. It is also important to be aware of the goals of your publisher, and to realize that these goals may run counter to the interests of the scientific community and the principle of fair open access. Strive for as many papers as possible to be open in your journal and resist unwelcome developments, such as increases in author processing charges.

In recent years, many editors and boards have become frustrated with their publishers and the system of academic publication. In 2015, the editors of *Lingua*

dropped their Elsevier journal and established Glossa; the DuJAL board left Benjamins in 2020 to continue the journal elsewhere, and recently the editors of Syntax left their Wiley journal to start Syntactic Theory and Research (STAR). According to Retraction Watch, at least fifty boards have taken this step already. In other words, you are free to leave (*The Retraction Watch Mass Resignations List*, n.d.).

Academic societies

In an ideal situation, academic publishing is be organized by trusted parties that subscribe to and follow the principles of diamond publishing. This is why academic societies can play a key role. In addition, it can be difficult to set up sound financial structures for diamond journals. The most successful ones are those supported by membership-driven academic societies. This is why it was such an excellent move by EuroSLA to launch the *JESLA* journal. *DuJAL* belongs to the Dutch Association of Applied linguistics. Their members carry the operational costs, thus creating financially secure circumstances for these journals. It would be fantastic if other societies followed suit.

Conclusion

I have argued that the current system of open access publishing has become untenable because it reinforces inequity and undermines research quality. This is driven by high-cost APC-based business models, quantity-focused research and evaluation practices, and - potentially - the use of generative AI in scientific publishing. If we continue to pursue open access publication within such a system, then our goals of increased equity, transparency, and better science are jeopardized. Only diamond open access platforms on non-commercial infrastructure can help us move away from this system, especially if such platforms are supported or owned academic communities and societies. Changing the existing dynamics will not be easy, but we have more power than we think. Ultimately, academic publishing relies primarily on the time and knowledge that we as authors, reviewers and editors invest in it. Many of us will not be able to make radical changes to our current publication practices, but if we redirect just a little of our labour towards fairer, community-owned publishing models, then change is possible.

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